

Immunofluorescence for protein binder validation

ID: SP000R-H

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Protocol description

Protocol for low/middle scale protein binder validation. It is set up to assess colocalization of binder-FLAG signal and overexpressed SLC-Strep-HA and/or compare binder specificity in wild type cells and knockout cells.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HEK293 Jump-in T-rex cells (TFS)▪ HCT116 cells (ATCC)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Poly-L-lysine (Sigma, #P6282)▪ PBS (1x) (Sigma, #D8537)▪ FCS (Biowest, #S1810)▪ 100 % Triton-X (Sigma, #9036-19-5)▪ Formaldehyde 37% (Merck, #1040021000)▪ High-affinity binders (nanobodies, sybodies, scFABs...)▪ anti-FLAG M2 (Sigma, #F1804)▪ anti-HA (C29F4) Rabbit mAb (Cell Signaling, #3724)▪ AlexaFluor488 Goat anti-Mouse IgG (Invitrogen, #A-11001)▪ AlexaFluor594 Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (Invitrogen, #A-11012)▪ Counter-staining Hoechst 33342 (TFS, # 62249)▪ ProLong medium Diamond (Invitrogen, #P36934)▪ 24-well plates (Costar, #3527)▪ Microscopic cover slips (Marienfeld GmbH, #0117530)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Zeiss LSM 700

Reagents setup

Poly-L-lysine.

Plates coated with Poly-L-lysine (for HEK293 cells only) can be prepared the day before and stored at 4°C (*Note 1*).

Blocking solution

10% FCS + 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS (1x)

Always prepare fresh.

Blocking solution without detergent

10% FCS in PBS (1x)

Use for non-permeabilization conditions.

PFA

4% FA in PBS (1x)

Always prepare fresh.

Antibodies:

- Binder (FLAG tagged): 0.05 mg/ml in blocking solution
- Primary antibodies:

(to detect binder) anti-FLAG M2 mouse 1:1000 in blocking solution

(to detect SLC) anti-HA (C29F4) Rabbit mAb 1:400 in blocking solution

- Secondary antibodies:

(to detect FLAG) Mouse AlexaFluor 488 use 1:500 in blocking solution

(to detect HA) Rabbit AlexaFluor 594 use 1:500 in blocking solution

- Counter stain solution:

Use Hoechst 33342 1:1000 in PBS (1x).

Procedure

Plate coating and cell seeding / day 1

1. Insert sterile glass coverslips into 24 well plate.
2. Aseptically coat the coverslips with Poly-L-lysine: apply ~400 μ L/well and incubate for 5 minutes under the hood.
3. Remove the solution and rinse twice with sterile tissue culture grade water.
4. Allow to dry for at least 2 hours before introducing cells and medium.
5. Induce protein expression by culturing cells in DMEM 10%FBS, 1% P/S medium containing 1 μ g/ml DOX.
6. Seed 1 ml medium with 1.5×10^5 Hek293 cells/well 1×10^5 HCT116 cells/well and incubate at least 24 h at 37°C.

Cell fixation and immunofluorescence staining / day 2

1. Aspirate medium carefully using a yellow tip instead of the 2ml pipette.
2. Do NOT wash cells in PBS!
3. Fix cells with 500 μ l 4% FA in PBS (1x) for 15 min, RT, rocking.
4. Properly dispose of fixation solution (under the lab hood, appropriate container!).
5. Add 1 ml blocking solution and incubate for 1h, RT, rocking.
6. Add 300 μ l Binders at the appropriate dilution in blocking solution for 2h, RT, rocking.
7. Wash 3 x 5 min in 500 μ l blocking solution, RT, rocking.
8. Add 300 μ l of primary antibodies in blocking solution for 2h, RT, rocking.
9. Wash 3 x 5 min in 500 μ l blocking solution, RT, rocking.
10. Add 300 μ l of secondary antibody in blocking solution for 1 h, RT, rocking.
11. Wash 3 x 5 min in 500 μ l blocking solution, RT, rocking.
12. Counter stain with 300 μ l Hoechst 33342 1:1000 in PBS (1x) 10 min, RT, rocking.
13. Wash 500 μ l 1 x PBS (1x).
14. Mount with ProLong medium diamond (Invitrogen).

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Additional notes

Note 1: use vacuum pump + 2 ml pipette to pick up the coverslips. Also keep PLL, you can recycle it!

Data availability

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards>

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.